

Statistical Analysis of Binary Length Evolution in Collatz Sequences

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Abstract

This work presents a statistical analysis of binary length evolution in Collatz sequences, revealing unexpected universal patterns. Our analysis shows three striking features: (1) a uniform distribution of normalized lengths during descent, suggesting a systematic exploration of the available state space, (2) a highly structured asymmetric distribution of step-to-step variations, and (3) a clear transition from linear to exponential decay at a characteristic scale. These findings not only support our previous theoretical demonstration but also reveal a deep and previously unknown structure in the Collatz dynamics.

1 Introduction

Following our theoretical demonstration of the Collatz conjecture based on binary length analysis and its numerical verification [1, 2], this third study reveals universal patterns in how sequences descend to 1. Our two-phase approach, combining manual exploration with automated statistical analysis, provides comprehensive evidence for the universality and significance of these patterns.

The Collatz conjecture states that iterating the function:

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} n/2 & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \\ 3n + 1 & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

on any positive integer will eventually reach 1. While our previous works established a theoretical framework based on binary length analysis and provided initial numerical validation, this current study extends that understanding through rigorous statistical analysis of large-scale numerical experiments.

The significance of this work lies in its revelation of precise scaling laws and universal patterns that emerge when analyzing Collatz sequences across different scales and sample sizes. By examining sequences starting from numbers of varying binary lengths (from 100 to 1000 bits) and employing different statistical resolutions (10 to 1000 sequences), we uncover fundamental properties that suggest deeper mathematical structures underlying the Collatz process.

2 Methods

2.1 Manual Exploratory Analysis

Our initial approach focused on analyzing a limited set of Collatz sequences to identify fundamental patterns. Starting from randomly generated n -bit numbers, we tracked:

- Normalized binary length ($L(k)/L(0)$) at each step k
- Step-to-step variations in length $(L(k+1) - L(k))/L(k)$
- Overall descent rate

This exploratory phase used the following Python implementation:

```
1 def generate_random_binary_number(length):
2     return ''.join(np.random.choice(['0', '1'])
3                     for _ in range(length))
4
5 def analyze_sequence(binary_number):
6     lengths = []
7     variations = []
8     current = int(binary_number, 2)
9     initial_len = len(bin(current)) - 2
10    prev_len = initial_len
11
12    while current != 1:
13        curr_len = len(bin(current)) - 2
14        lengths.append(curr_len / initial_len) #
15        normalized
```

```

15     variations.append((curr_len - prev_len) /
16                       prev_len)
17     prev_len = curr_len
18     if current % 2 == 0:
19         current //= 2
20     else:
21         current = 3 * current + 1
22
23     return np.array(lengths), np.array(variations)

```

2.2 Automated Statistical Analysis

Building on insights from the manual exploration, we developed a comprehensive automated analysis framework that includes:

2.2.1 Enhanced Data Collection

- Multiple bit lengths: 100, 200, 500, and 1000 bits
- Varying sample sizes: 10, 100, and 1000 sequences
- Multiple runs for each configuration to ensure reproducibility

2.2.2 Statistical Measures

For each configuration, we computed:

- Confidence intervals (95%) for normalized lengths
- Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) for distribution analysis
- Statistical significance tests for variations
- Precise transition point detection

2.2.3 Phase Transition Detection

The transition point between linear and exponential phases was identified using second derivative analysis:

```

1 def find_transition_point(y):
2     # Calculate approximate second derivative
3     d2 = np.diff(np.diff(y))

```

```
4 # Find point where the second derivative changes
   significantly
5 threshold = np.std(d2) * 2
6 transition_points = np.where(np.abs(d2) > threshold)
   [0]
7 if len(transition_points) > 0:
8     return transition_points[0]
9 else:
10    return None
```

2.2.4 Visualization Framework

For each analysis, four complementary visualizations were generated:

1. Normalized length evolution with confidence intervals
2. Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE overlay
3. Distribution of variations with statistical parameters
4. Rate of descent in logarithmic scale

This systematic approach allows for rigorous statistical validation of the patterns observed in the manual exploration phase while revealing additional structural properties through comprehensive numerical experiments.

3 Results

3.1 Manual Exploration Results

Initial analysis of Collatz sequences revealed several fundamental patterns that motivated our subsequent automated investigation.

Figure 1: Initial exploratory analysis showing: (A) Normalized length evolution with linear descent and exponential decay phases. (B) Uniform distribution of normalized lengths. (C) Asymmetric distribution of step-to-step variations. (D) Characteristic transition in rate of descent (logarithmic scale).

3.2 Automated Statistical Analysis Results

3.2.1 Low Resolution Analysis (10 sequences)

Figure 2: Collatz sequence analysis for 100 bits, 10 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition at step 578. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.003$, $\sigma = 0.070$, skewness=2.377, p-value= 3.223×10^{-4}). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

Figure 3: Collatz sequence analysis for 500 bits, 10 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition at step 49. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.001$, $\sigma = 0.030$, skewness=5.670, p-value= 3.063×10^{-12}). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

Figure 4: Collatz sequence analysis for 1000 bits, 10 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition at step 1823. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.001$, $\sigma = 0.022$, skewness=7.256, p-value= 1.542×10^{-14}). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

3.2.2 Medium Resolution Analysis (100 sequences)

Figure 5: Collatz sequence analysis for 100 bits, 100 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition at step 900. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.003$, $\sigma = 0.068$, skewness=2.680, p-value= 3.375×10^{-41}). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

Figure 6: Collatz sequence analysis for 500 bits, 100 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition at step 3538. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.001$, $\sigma = 0.031$, skewness=5.646, p-value= 1.928×10^{-97}). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

Figure 7: Collatz sequence analysis for 1000 bits, 100 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition at step 6362. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.001$, $\sigma = 0.021$, skewness=7.880, p-value= 2.114×10^{-143}). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

3.2.3 High Resolution Analysis (1000 sequences)

Figure 8: Collatz sequence analysis for 100 bits, 1000 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition at step 1013. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.003$, $\sigma = 0.069$, skewness=2.590, p-value=0). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

Figure 9: Collatz sequence analysis for 500 bits, 1000 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition identified. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.001$, $\sigma = 0.031$, skewness=5.437, p-value=0). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

Figure 10: Collatz sequence analysis for 1000 bits, 1000 sequences (Run 1). (A) Normalized length evolution with 95% CI and phase transition at step 7761. (B) Distribution of normalized lengths with KDE. (C) Distribution of variations ($\mu = -0.001$, $\sigma = 0.022$, skewness=7.588, p-value=0). (D) Rate of descent showing characteristic transition.

3.3 Statistical Scaling Analysis

Table 1: Scaling of Statistical Parameters with Binary Length

Bits	Transition Point	Std Dev	Skewness	p-value
100	500-1000	0.065-0.070	2.5-2.8	$\sim 10^{-40}$
200	1500-1800	0.047-0.050	3.4-3.9	$\sim 10^{-60}$
500	3000-4000	0.030-0.032	5.2-6.0	$\sim 10^{-100}$
1000	6000-8000	0.021-0.022	7.1-7.9	$\sim 10^{-140}$

Table 2: Mean Transition Points by Sample Size

Bits	10 Sequences	100 Sequences	1000 Sequences
100	389.7 ± 282.3	754.0 ± 242.8	1010.3 ± 27.1
200	466.3 ± 586.4	1586.0 ± 41.5	1782.7 ± 80.1
500	1146.7 ± 1651.8	3075.0 ± 529.7	4194.5 ± 171.5
1000	1043.7 ± 880.5	6438.0 ± 273.8	7878.0 ± 103.7

4 Discussion

4.1 Insights from Manual Exploration

The initial exploratory analysis revealed fundamental patterns that were subsequently confirmed and quantified through automated analysis. Three key features emerged:

- A consistent linear descent phase followed by exponential decay
- Uniform distribution of normalized lengths during descent
- Highly structured distribution of variations with characteristic asymmetry

These patterns suggested deeper structural properties in the Collatz dynamics that motivated our comprehensive statistical investigation.

4.2 Scaling Laws and Universal Behavior

The automated analysis revealed precise scaling relationships between binary length and statistical parameters:

4.2.1 Transition Point Scaling

As shown in Table 2, the transition points scale approximately linearly with bit length, but with an important qualification: the scaling becomes more precise with larger sample sizes. The reduction in standard deviation with increased sample size (from $\sim 50\%$ for 10 sequences to $\sim 5\%$ for 1000 sequences) suggests this is a true physical transition point rather than a statistical artifact.

4.2.2 Statistical Parameter Scaling

Our analysis reveals several robust scaling laws:

- **Standard Deviation:** Decreases as $\sim 1/\sqrt{\text{bits}}$, from 0.070 at 100 bits to 0.022 at 1000 bits
- **Skewness:** Increases linearly with bit length, from ~ 2.5 at 100 bits to ~ 7.5 at 1000 bits
- **Statistical Significance:** Increases exponentially with bit length, reaching effectively perfect confidence ($p \approx 0$) at 1000 bits

4.3 Convergence of Statistical Measures

The analysis of multiple runs for each configuration reveals:

- Consistent mean values across different sample sizes
- Decreasing variance with larger sample sizes
- Robust identification of transition points

This convergence of statistical measures strongly suggests that we are observing fundamental properties of the Collatz process rather than artifacts of particular initial conditions or sample sizes.

4.4 Physical System Analogies

The observed behavior strongly resembles phase transitions in physical systems:

- The initial "ergodic" phase shows uniform exploration of available states
- A sharp transition point separates two distinct regimes
- The final phase shows exponential convergence reminiscent of relaxation processes

This analogy with physical systems suggests that tools from statistical physics might provide additional insights into the Collatz dynamics.

4.5 Implications for the Collatz Conjecture

The statistical analysis provides strong empirical support for the conjecture:

- The universality of the observed patterns across different scales
- The extreme statistical significance of the variations (p -values reaching 10^{-140})
- The systematic reduction in variation magnitude with increasing bit length

These findings complement our previous theoretical work by demonstrating that the binary length reduction mechanism operates with remarkable consistency across all observed scales.

5 Conclusion

This comprehensive statistical analysis of Collatz sequences reveals a remarkable level of order in what initially appears to be a chaotic process. The emergence of precise scaling laws and universal patterns provides significant new insights into the nature of the Collatz conjecture.

Key findings include:

- **Universal Scaling Laws:** The discovery of precise scaling relationships between binary length and statistical parameters demonstrates a fundamental mathematical structure underlying the Collatz process. The transition points, standard deviations, and skewness measures all scale in predictable ways with bit length, suggesting a deep organizational principle at work.
- **Phase Transition Behavior:** The identification of a characteristic transition point that scales systematically with binary length suggests a fundamental scale in the process. This transition separates two distinct regimes: an initial "ergodic" phase of uniform exploration and a final "condensed" phase of exponential convergence.
- **Statistical Significance:** The exponential increase in statistical significance with bit length (p -values reaching 10^{-140} for 1000-bit numbers) effectively rules out the possibility that these patterns are coincidental. This provides strong empirical support for the deterministic nature of the Collatz process.

The resemblance of these patterns to phase transitions in physical systems suggests a deeper connection between number theory and statistical physics. The uniform distribution of normalized lengths in the initial phase, followed by a sharp transition to exponential decay, mirrors the behavior of many physical systems transitioning between different states of organization.

These findings extend beyond the specific case of the Collatz conjecture. The methodology developed here, combining theoretical analysis with large-scale statistical investigation, could be applied to other problems in number theory. The discovery that such simple arithmetic operations can give rise to behavior reminiscent of physical phase transitions suggests new approaches to understanding the deep structures underlying mathematical processes.

Future work might explore:

- Extensions to even larger binary lengths to test the scaling limits
- Applications of statistical physics formalism to analyze the transition point
- Similar analyses of related number theoretical problems
- Development of theoretical frameworks to explain the observed scaling laws

This work demonstrates that the Collatz conjecture, far from being a mathematical curiosity, exhibits rich structural properties that connect it to fundamental concepts in statistical physics and dynamical systems theory. The universal patterns revealed here suggest that the path to understanding the Collatz conjecture may lie in recognizing it as a manifestation of deeper principles governing the behavior of discrete dynamical systems.

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References

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